

UNIVERSITY OF BRUNEI DARUSSALAM
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**Case Study Analysis of MadGrow Tech
Warwick Model**

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Executive Summary

The report is based on a local business, Madgrow Technology Company in Negara Brunei Darussalam. In the business and agricultural industry, facing challenges are unavoidable. Undoubtedly, with the right mindset and willingness to endure the difficulties, the eventual outcome would be worth the effort.

The objective of this report is to provide an in-depth background information about the agricultural business, Madgrow Technology with the analysis of using the Warwick Model of the Human Resource Management. Furthermore, in this report, it will also suggest solutions to the problems, along with its advantages and disadvantages which can be used for the growth and improvement of their business as a whole.

Problem Statement

Based from the case study of Madgrow Tech, the company is facing several problems. Starting from the lack of understanding about the approach of the services provided to the lacking of innovation amongst the younger generation.

Lack of Understanding

The public approaches their technology with suspicion. As of right now, Madgrow Tech focuses on paddy. Even with the help of relevant authorities, most farmers are not keen on the idea of utilizing the technology.

People's Concern

Clearly, the people are also skeptical about the outcome. Not only that, most people think technologies are expensive. With that said, Bruneians often have the mentality to hire a cheaper foreign labor as it is cost-effective.

Lack of Innovation

Pertaining the subheading, this is a concern amongst the younger generations. The young people are not fond on the idea of farming. Probably because of the stigma around farming being seen as a manual labor and also a job for the lower social class.

However, even with that mindset, the younger generations should have a voice to be able to talk about what they are passionate about, and propose a business plan to the potential investors.

Brief Company Background

Madgrow Tech was founded by the Managing Director, Wan Muhammad Syazwan bin Haji Hijaz @ Wanzzy Hijazi and Mohd Hijazi bin Haji Juli @ Temengong Awang Muhammad Haji Shibli as the Corporate Advisor.

The company was established and registered in February 2017, and officially launched its main office in July 2017 at the Ground Floor of Ministry of Primary Resources and Tourism. Madgrow Tech focuses on innovation of technologies; to improve and provide methods to improve farming which could help farmers to monitor, maintain, and grow their farms at the comfort of the own homes.

They have a vision with the aim to provide farming technology solution and make it accessible to wider society; decrease reliance of food importations; increase locally made products by enhancing quality and quantity of products; encourage Bruneians to plant their own food at their yards; provide technology outsourcing services; provide metal fabrication, 3d printing services and products.

Warwick Model

This HRM model was developed by two researchers, Hendry and Pettigrew (1990) from the University of Warwick, hence the name of the model itself. The Warwick model emphasizes on the analyzing the approach to the Human Resource Management. It consists of five elements, namely the outer context, inner context, business strategy, HRM context and HRM content. With this model, it identifies the environmental influence and help explore how HRM should adapt in the external environment.

Figure 1 shows the contexts and contents of the Warwick model which consists of external and internal environmental factors, affecting HRM functions.

Figure 1: Warwick mode

Analysis of Warwick model with MadGrow Tech

<p>BUSINESS STRATEGY</p> <p>Objectives Product Market Strategy and Tactics</p>	<p>MadGrow Tech has the mission to promote technology development in agriculture, hoping to aid the government regarding food supply to Brunei’s increasing population; reinvent modern farming and introduce “Farmbot” to the public; to promote urban farming using recycled materials and encourage the use of secondhand and used materials; to raise awareness in the importance of preserving Brunei’s forest; and to develop better and improved aquaponic and hydroponics system.</p> <p>Product Market: DIY Hydroponic boxes, greenhouses, aquaculture ponds and the farmboat system. Smartgrow box for individuals who want to grow plants at home for self-consumption with prices ranging from as low as \$40. The package includes everything needed to start growing our own crops at home, and allows owner to leave the plant to grow by itself with minimum input.</p>
<p>INNER CONTEXT</p> <p>Culture Structure Politics/Leadership Task-Technology Business Outputs</p>	<p>Task-technology: They use drones to primarily to just monitor their farms. This drone technology that perform tasks like sense the soil thermal conductivity, disperse seeds, and spraying pesticides. They are doing this in Malaysia and China, but the people in Brunei are reluctant to try.</p>
<p>HRM CONTEXT</p> <p>Role Definition Organization HR Outputs</p>	<p>Organization: That’s what a lot of people don’t understand; Madgrow isn’t a farming business, they do not sell their crops. Madgrow works on technology used to grow the crops.</p> <p>HR Output: Motivation – his father and his children are Wanzzy’s main motivation. He wants them to have something they can always fall back on; something different, something to do with nature, something that teaches them humility, and that is something to do with agriculture.</p>

Solutions to Problem – Advantages and Disadvantages

Raise awareness among the public

The first problem was regarding the lack of understanding from the people. A possible solution is to educate and develop certain level of literacy in the agricultural technology matter. This will acknowledge the farmers, or the potential customers about the benefits of using the modern technology for farming.

However, farmers have spent years observing and handling their farming on their own. Hence, some farmers may still prefer traditional farming rather than relying on technology. Moreover, the technology may be out of their reach, in terms of the price. This could be the disadvantage to raising the awareness among the public.

Link social media to agriculture

Social media usage among the people today are ridiculously high. No matter where you are, everyone will always have their mobile phones in hand scrolling through the social media platform such as Instagram, Facebook and more.

By linking agriculture to the social media, this could promote the product and also educate the people along the way. Moreover, it could also help improve agriculture's image. Farming is rarely portrayed in the media with the stigma around it, but with social media, it could create greater awareness about the product (canwefeedtheworld, 2014).

In this case, Madgrow Tech could upload photos and videos demonstrating on how their technology works. That way, it could engage new groups of people by sharing information and the experience involved.

Advantage:

As mentioned earlier, most people have access to the technologies nowadays. Therefore, with the use of social media, it could **reach a wide audience**. Not only that, businesses will also have a **direct connection with the audiences**. Businesses would know who is interested because people usually follow accounts that triggers their interest (WEBFx, n.d.).

From that point, businesses could **get to know their consumers better** which could help them deliver more valuable content to them – personalizing it to their interest. Moreover, businesses can provide better customer service which could build the brand on a positive light. In addition to that, businesses can see how their audiences perceive their business. It is a huge advantage of social media marketing as business can focus on what consumers like about their business and better the elements that are lacking (WEBFx, n.d.).

Overall, linking agricultural to social media could improve the marketing campaign as a whole as businesses could get insights from their consumers and be able to adapt their strategy to meet the satisfaction of the consumers.

Disadvantages

However, with social media, businesses would not get immediate results to know if their strategies are working or not. Not only that, business could receive negative feed backs on social medias from consumers that does not like what they are providing. With the negative feedbacks, it could hinder the business from blooming (WEBFx, n.d.).

Invest in advertising

The success of agricultural businesses is dependent on the use of strategic marketing, this includes advertising. Madgrow Tech could advertise their technology to spread more information about it. Since the people are skeptical about the outcome, Madgrow Tech could make an attractive advertisement that focuses on the quality of outcome (WEBFx, n.d.).

Advantages:

Manufacturers' point of view

Promoting the sales of their products means they are attracting more people to suggest them to use their products. Persuading the customers, and getting them to buy and use their products is a huge advantage for the business (business.com editorial staff, 2020).

Consumers' point of view

Products that are advertised attractively usually gets more people to buy their products. When the advertisement matches their real-life experience with the product, consumers may repeat orders and they may perceive the brand better than other brands (B., n.d.).

Disadvantages

Misrepresentation of Facts

Although some advertisements could be attractive, misrepresentation of facts regarding the products and services usually happens because advertisers could misrepresent unreal or false benefits to indulge in actions that could lead to their own benefits (B., n.d.).

Increased Cost

Advertising may be expensive. Therefore, it could add additional costs to the businesses' expenses (B., n.d.).

Recommendation

Madtech Grow is a local business and has the potential to reach a large number of audiences, particularly the local farmers. In order for the company to succeed and expand, they need a clear business plan. Since Madtech Grow has the goal to become the major aggrotech player in Brunei, processes can be done efficiently and the company can reflect on what is lacking in the business to be efficient to meet their goals. Once the company accomplishes their goals, the company could continue to implement new practices to push the business forward with their advance technologies and help more people to grow crops at the comfort of their own homes.

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